

INVESTIGATION OF A METHOD OF PREDICTING THE DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTIC OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL STRUCTURES WITH LOWER NOISE AND FORCE-STANDING

Zhu Ming Wang Zhengping

(Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xian, Shaanxi 710072, China)

ABSTRACT

In present paper a method of predicting mechanics-lower noise characteristic of composite material structures in design of Airplanes is proposed.

The method takes into consideration not only external loading, materials, nonlinearity of deformation and damping, But also variation of damping with vibrating displacement, velocity and acceleration as well as a relation to frequencies. In consideration of sound excitation and sound-Vibration coupling. Necessary formulae are derived and a optimal program is compiled using finite element method for computing nonlinear structural dynamic responses.

Keywords: composite, Noise control, dynamic responses, finite element software for nonlinear structure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Optimum Design of low-noise structures in the design of airplanes becomes a important probleme and has more and more attention. The expenditure of work hours and cost due to remedial process of supplementang modification for reducing noise, after manufacturing of airplanes might be avoided. Therefore it is necessary to put up an investigation on theoretic calculation and experiment for lower noise structures. The present paper is related to the study of finite element calculation for structures with lower noise and force-standing put forward by reference^[1]. The structural calculation of noise reduction for airplanes may be divided into two parts: First, sound radiation charecteristics of structures under sound excitation. Second, sound radiation charecteristics of structures in consideration of sound and vibration couhling. The method could be used for design of new airplanes, and supplementary modification of made airplanes for noise reduction as well. So far the analysis of composite material structures with lower noise and force-standing using finite element method has not been reported, so it should be considered as a new attempt.

2. STRUCTURE MODEL

structures with lower noise and fore-standing, given by reference^[1] mainly are honeycomb sandwich structures and in some ways to increase damping, so the lower noise strutures generally are made up of thicker plates or shells.

3. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Recently, The methods for lower noise structure analysis include ones of complex stiffness, energy

and model. The finite element method has not been found in public references. The methods of energy and complex stiffness are only for analyzing damping characteristics, not suitable to complex structures. The characteristics of system vibration could be completely taken into account by the methods of modal and finite element, because of using stiffness matrix and damping matrix, for total characteristics of structural stiffness and damping.

It should be noticed, not only the deformation of composite materials is nonlinear, but damping nonlinearly as well, which mainly show the change of damping with displacement, velocity, acceleration of vibration and frequency. So modal method only used in the range of micro amplitude and linear vibration.

Noise excitation of vehicles is often in high sound-level, particularly, The wall-plate structures near engine often bear a sound-level higher than 160dB and a sound-level around 125~135dB out of the cabin of a large passenger plane. In such a condition, there exists a large response deflection of wall-plate structures under high noise excitation, so nonlinear problems of geometry, caused by large deflection response should be considered. therefore the finite element method for calculation of nonlinear dynamic response of composite sandwich structures is adopted.

4. CALCULATING METHOD OF SOUND INSULATING CHARACTERISTICS OF PLATE-SHELLS

For ideal one-dimensional model, the motion equation of insulation board under sound field can be set up as following:

$$M\ddot{\xi} + R\dot{\xi} + K\xi = P(X^-, t) - P(X^+, t) \quad (1)$$

In the equation, X^- , X^+ represent the loads exerted on two side of the board. It's observed that if incident sound field and emissive field caused by board motion are assumed, the above equation can be solved. But in engineering application a revised equation or experimental measurement is often used to calculate the value of sound insulation. Because of the complication of engineering structures, it's difficult to obtain a precise result only by analysis method and approximate calculation. several corrected coefficients or values must be introduced, thus a larger error would be brought about. This restricts the application of the equation in engineering.

For wall-plate structures of the airplane, characteristics of sound insulation under outer sound excitation should be affected by several parameters such as geometry, boundary joint, stiffness, damping and mass et al, In this paper, the board-shell structure was treated as a discrete system with several degrees of freedom, by using of FEM. A dynamic structural response equation taken all parameters mentioned above into consideration was set up, and thus sound insulation characteristics of various antinoise structures can be calculated.

According to generalized Hamilton principle. A new FEM dynamic structural equilibrium equation in consideration of dissipation of energy caused by damping was obtained.

$$\begin{aligned}
 [m]\{\ddot{U}\} + [c]\{\dot{U}\} + [k]\{U\} &= \{F(t)\} \quad (2) \\
 [k] &= \int_{ve} [B]^T [D] [B] dv \\
 [c] &= \int_{ve} C [N]^T [N] dv \\
 [m] &= \int_{ve} [N]^T [N] dv
 \end{aligned}$$

$[c]$ is the damping matrix of structures. Factors influencing structural damping are complicated.

ed, so, Rayleigh damping is used

$$[c] = \alpha[M] + \beta[k] \quad (3)$$

For damping ratio ξ under certain resonance frequency ω , the following relation can be set up

$$\alpha + \beta\omega^2 = 2\omega\xi \quad (4)$$

α, β can be defined by experiments or experience.

With reference to conventional linear system, It's a second order linear differential equation, and can be solved directly with common dynamic response calculation method. but for composite materials nonlinear system is not suitable. Because of nonlinear factors such as large deflection and strain of composite materials, the stiffness matrix will change with displacement, at the same time, displacement is a function of time, then the matrix $[k]$ is no longer a constant matrix. It is obvious that damping matrix is a function of time from equation (3), considering the distribution of sound load on the airplane structure equation (2) may be written:

$$[m]\{\ddot{U}(t)\} + [c(t)]\{\dot{U}(t)\} + [k(t)]\{U(t)\} = \{F(x, y, z, t)\} \quad (5)$$

This is a second order nonlinear differential equation. By solving the equation group nonlinear dynamic response analysis for sandwich antinoise structure of composite material can be obtained.

In general, wall-plate structures of vehicles are excited by noise of airplane (jet noise, aerodynamic noise) with a sweep incident on the structure, so it might be supposed in engineering practice, that load $F(t, y, z, t)$ may approximately separated into two variables. one is a certain function in space $f(x, y, z)$, another is a random function $g(t)$;

$$F(x, y, z, t) = f(x, y, z) \cdot g(t)$$

If sound load is uniformly distributed, it takes $f(x, y, z) = 0$. So whatever sound load is in a wide or narrow band random vibration or self-noise, equation (6) may be used directly to load in the form of time spectrum.

5. FEM MODEL

9 joints logranging and 8 joints Heteresis three dimensional retrograde equivalent elements are used (fig. 1), two fundamental assumptions for elements of curved shell are used:

1. normal of middle surface before deformation still remains straight line after deformation.

2. Stress component along thickness of could be neglected. To every joint of elements 5 degrees of freedom, 3 displacements and 2 independent normal Turning angles are taken and the effect of shear deformation is considered.

In order to make the curved shell elements suitable to composite laminations and sandwich structures a laminated model is used, the fundamental idea is to carry out a dispersed treatment along the thickness direction ξ (fig. 2). Each layer after the treatment may be regarded as

Fig 1

Fig 2

two dimensions. So stiffness matrix and mass matrix of elements may be written as a form of the following:

$$[k]^e = \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 [B_i]^T [D_i] [B_i] |J| d\xi d\eta \cdot \Delta \xi_i$$

$$[m]^e = \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 [N_i]^T [N_i] |J| d\xi d\eta \cdot \Delta \xi_i$$

6. CALCULATION OF NONLINEAR DYNAMIC RESPONSE

The differential equation group (5) is, total equilibrium equation consisted of single equation group, to solve these equations time dimension may be discretized according to the FEM, thus it becomes a four dimensional question and increases degrees of freedom, therefore differential treatment in time domain. To find the dynamic response of such a system, the finite element method in space domain and the differential method in time domain are combined, it is a semi-discretization finite element.

As in (5) dynamic system damping and stiffness are nonlinear acceleration is still linear, and the mass matrix $[m]$ is invariant with time, Then, the generalized linear-acceleration method, i. e. Wilson- θ method can be used. In consideration of nonlinear effect integral procedure of Wilson- θ method should be improved. As large deflection and strain have an effect on the rigid body and damping matrix, so it is necessary to reconstruct the effective stiffness matrix for every interval of time. Tangent stiffness method or load increment method are used to solve the equivalent equations of static balance for obtaining values of nonlinear displacement. For finding the dynamic response, the procedure of solution will be stated as follows:

a. primary calculation

(1) preset $\{U_0\}$, $\{\dot{U}\}$ and $\{\ddot{U}\}$

(2) select the time interval and calculate integral constant

$$\theta = 1.4$$

$$a_0 = \frac{6}{(\theta \Delta t)^2}, \quad a_1 = \frac{3}{\theta \Delta t}, \quad a_2 = 2a_1$$

$$a_3 = \frac{\theta \Delta t}{2}, \quad a_4 = \frac{a_0}{\theta}, \quad a_5 = \frac{-a_2}{\theta}$$

$$a_6 = 1 - \frac{3}{\theta}, \quad a_7 = \frac{\Delta t}{2}, \quad a_8 = \frac{\Delta t^2}{6}$$

(3) set up $[B_0]$ $[G]$ matrixes for large deflection and strain calculation.

b. Calculation of each time interval

(1) Set up mass matrix $[m]$ and stiffness matrix considering geometry nonlinearity $[k]$.

(2) Calculate effective load in interval $t + \Delta t$.

$$\{\hat{F}t + \theta \Delta t\} = \{F_t\} + \theta \{F_{t+\Delta t}\} - \theta \{F_t\} + [m] \{a_0 \{U_t\} + a_2 \{\dot{U}_t\} + 2 \{\ddot{U}_t\} + [c] \{a_1 \{U_t\} + 2 \{\dot{U}_t\} + a_3 \{\ddot{U}_t\}\}$$

(3) To solve the displacement at $t + \Delta t$

- i) Add load increment
- ii) Reestablish stiffness matrix $[k]$ and damping matrix $[c]$ considering nonlinear effect.
- iii) Establish effective matrix $[k^*]$ and triangularization.
- iv) Solve equilibrium equation of equivalent static force.
- v) Repeat ii) till satisfied accuracy.
- vi) Back to i).

(4) Calculate displacement, velocity and acceleration at $t + \Delta t$.

$$\{U_{t+\Delta t}\} = a_4(\{U_{t+\theta\Delta t}\} - \{U_t\}) + a_5\{\dot{U}_t\} + a_6\{\ddot{U}_t\}$$

$$\{\dot{U}_{t+\Delta t}\} = \{\dot{U}_t\} + a_7(\{\ddot{U}_{t+\Delta t}\}) + \{\ddot{U}_t\}$$

$$\{U_{t+\Delta t}\} = \{U_t\} + \Delta t\{\dot{U}_t\} + a_8(\{\ddot{U}_{t+\Delta t}\}) + \{\ddot{U}_t\}$$

After finishing the calculation of nonlinear dynamic response vibration displacement, velocity and acceleration at each point of plate-shells in any time can be obtained. It is demonstrated by research and experiment of the surface vibration of large samples that degrees of noise level are dependent on amplitude of surface vibration velocity, so following relation between noise pressure radiated from structures and vibration velocity is obtained

$$L_v = L_p = 20 \log \frac{v}{v_0} = 20 \log \frac{p}{p_0}$$

v_0 , p_0 represent reference datum velocity and sound pressure respectively. For structural vibration coefficient smaller than 1 in low frequency range above equation can be used with the addition of modified coefficients and terms obtained by experiment.

There exists a number of calculating methods for sound insulation. mean square value of space and time domains can be directly used to describe lower-noise characteristic of plate-shells, i. e. sound insulating value $T_L = 20 \log(\sqrt{\bar{v}_o}/\sqrt{\bar{v}})$, \bar{v}_o is the mean square value of velocity in outer sound field. Under the same condition power spectrum density can also be used to express sound insulating characteristic, i. e. $T_L = 10 \log(S_e(w)/S(10))$, $S_e(w)$ is the power spectrum density under pressure of outer sound field.

7. CALCULATION AND ANALYSIS

In order to verify feasibility of the method described above, a complete nonlinear dynamic response program for composite lamination or sandwich plate-shell structures was worked out, which is capable of calculating antinoise characteristic. The values of stress and strain of plate-shell structures. Calculation of a composite sandwich plate, was carried out, Upper and lower plates of the sandwich structure ($h = 1.5$ mm thickness) are made of Carbon-epoxy laminated plate, and the core is of honeycomb glassfiber reinforced plastic with 14 mm height. sound insulation curve is drawn in fig. 3. According to results of calculation, It shows:

1. The trend in distribution of the curve is in accordance with the experimental results.

2. Coefficient α in lower damping Rayleigh is smaller, and β is maximum, so the value of sound insulation mainly depends on the toughness of plate-shells. In case of decrease of β and gradually increase of α with the increase of frequency there appears a zone of middle frequency of quality control. Therefore Rayleigh damping is appropriate to calculate dynamic response of antinoise structures.

3. composite sandwich structures possess good lower noise characteristic and could be used as a antinoise structures of airplanes in addition of other auxiliary lower noise means.

4. The method and program described above can meet requirements of accuracy of noise and mechanical characteristics in Aeronautical Engineering, It could be used for the design of new airplanes and the budget of remedial process of noise reduction, which will save manpower, material resources and reduce economic consumption.

Fig 3

It should be noticed finally, factors α, β are defined by experiment, which effect the calculation accuracy. Since we haven't enough time, it would be necessary to do more experiments to select optimum one of composite structures. In addition, the accuracy of calculation is related to time, interval, load characteristic, structural frequency and damping, a good deal of research work should be carried out. The method is now being used to the design of lower noise structure of y-x modified airplane.

Reference

1. Zhu, M. , Wang, Z. P. , Chen, X. A. , A Study on the Antinoise and Forcestanding combined structures, pp776-781 Proceedings of the second international symposium on composite materials and structures, 1992.
2. White, R. G. , Walker, J. G. , Noise And Vibration, Ellis Horwood Limited, 1982.